

ELEPHANT

IN THE LAB

SHORT ANALYSIS

11000111 authors

Short title	11000111 authors
Long title	Bibliometrics for the Subject Areas Computer Science and Decision Sciences for the 20 Highest Performing Authors
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Description

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Computer Science* is 4 on average with a maximum of 21 authors. The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.1 per year in the

respective time period (Figure 1). The articles in this analysis ($n = 1558$) were cited 11.4 times on average with a maximum of 199 citations.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA COMPUTER SCIENCE

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.1
Number of articles = 1558

Figure 1: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Computer Science*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Decision Sciences* is 3.1 on average with a maximum of 13 authors (Figure 2). The mean number of coauthors is decreasing by 0.02 per year in the respective time period. The articles in this analysis ($n = 192$) were cited 7 times on average and 35 as maximum which is the smallest number.

SHORT ANALYSIS

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA DECISION SCIENCES

Increase of co-authors per year = <0.1
Number of articles = 192

Figure 2: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Decision Sciences*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

Methodology

The results of the Advanced search in Scopus were restricted by an algorithm with

- a time period of publishing (2010 to 2016)
- the document types (articles or reviews),

- and a quantitative limitation regarding the publication output (articles by the 20 highest performing authors with the most Scopus listed articles in every subject area).

For details and code see Schmidt et al. [2017](#).

References

Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). Methodology for the analysis of authors using meta data from Scopus. [Elephant in the lab](#). [Link](#).